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A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“THE VALUE OF HUMAN RIGHTS”

A yearning voice calls out asking for the truth.

No chains can restrain what, in essence, needs to be free.

A poem burning for dignity. When standing quiet, it gives birth to hope.

While whispering truth joined with marching feet,
confirming the fact that: each life must raise each voice must ring.

The claim that exists within us, cannot be crushed with:

No sword, law, or crown sealed with walls.

To love, speak or simply live, carefree, unrestricted. Bound to no hierarchy.

But standing shoulder to shoulder with the feeling and loving pair above.

Made to -never- kneel, but born: To dream, have clear passionate minds and indescribable peace. Oh how much more. “Darkness shall fall before the light. Power shall surrender to what is right.”

Kindness shall always lift the wronged and abused while Justice shall pour down like summer.
In every tear human rights fly. Defying hope while burning the premature ends of night and truth. Together letting the flame persist eternally.